

LEUKEMIA AND ITS TYPES, CAUSES, TREATMENT METHODS.

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Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada. Leykoz(Oq qon)kassalini kelib chiqish sabablari, Leykoz kasalligi bilan kasallangan bemorlar va ularning organizmidagi o'zgarishlar davolash turlari haqida yoritib beriladi.

Аннотация: В данной статье описаны причины лейкоза, виды лечения больных лейкозом и изменения в их организме.

Abstract: This article describes the causes of leukemia, the types of treatment for patients with leukemia and the changes in their body.

Kalit so'zi: Leykoz, O'tkir, Surunkali, Sitogenez, Sitostatik, Qon.

Ключевое слово: лейкемия, хронический, острый, цитогенез, цитостатик, кровь.

Key word: Leukemia, chronic, sharp, cytogenesis, cytotoxic, blood.

Leukemia (leukemia, leukemia, white blood disease) is a clonal malignant (neoplastic) disease of the hematopoietic system. Leukemias include a wide group of diseases that differ in their etiology. In leukemias, a poor-quality clone can appear from immature hematopoietic cells of the bone marrow, as well as from maturing and mature blood cells. Types of leukemia disease: Acute leukemia, Chronic leukemia.

Acute - from immature cells (blasts)

Chronic - maturing and mature cells.

It should also be noted that acute leukemia never turns into a chronic form, and in chronic cases, attacks are not observed. For chronic leukemias, "attacks" are characterized by blast crises, the blood image of which resembles an acute state.

According to the degree of differentiation of tumor cells

Undifferentiated

Blastly

Sitar leukemias

According to cytogenesis

According to cytogenesis, acute leukemia is divided into:

Lymphoblastic, Myeloid, Monoblastic, Myelomonoblastic, Erythromeloblastic, Megakaryoblastic, Undifferentiated.

Chronic leukemia is represented by the following types:

Myelocytic origin: chronic myelocytic, chronic neutrophilic, chronic eosinophilic, chronic basophilic, myelosclerosis.

The main clinical signs of acute leukemia: the abundance of blast cells and their predominance (more than 30%, usually 60-90%). "Leukemic collapse" is the disappearance of intermediate forms of cells against the background of many blasts. leaving

Simultaneous presence of abasophilia and aneosinophilia.

Rapidly developing anemia.

The main clinical signs of chronic leukemia: (symptoms are the same, but just the opposite). Low or complete absence of blast cells (less than 30%, often 1-2%). Absence of "leukemic collapse", or the presence of intermediate forms of cells (promyelocytes and myelocytes).

Basophil-eosinophil association, that is, the presence of basophilia and eosinophilia at the same time.

Anemia that develops gradually.

Diagnosis. Morphological studies are of great importance in the diagnosis of white blood cell disease. The main methods of morphological diagnosis during life are trepanobiopsy of the iliac bone or study of bone marrow biopsies and peripheral blood smears obtained from the function of the sternum and other organs.

Treatment methods. In chronic leukemia, we choose supportive tactics from all sides. Our goal is to delay or prevent the development of complications. Acute leukemia requires urgent therapy, which includes taking high doses of chemotherapeutic agents. Chemotherapy allows the body to get rid of white blood cells. After that, if required, a transplant of bone marrow cells from a healthy donor is prescribed.

Cytostatics are drugs that suppress the growth of atypical cells. They are administered intravenously or orally in tablet form. Different variants of the disease require a specific treatment regimen. According to the recommendations of the World Health Organization, each specialist can follow different therapy regimens. After the exact variant of leukemia is determined (taking into account the cell composition), the patient is prescribed chemotherapy in several courses according to the necessary scheme: First course: aimed at destroying harmful cells. Its duration is determined individually and can be several months.

After the successful completion of the first course, supportive therapy is prescribed - the patient is given cytostatics in the previous doses and quantities.

The last stage: this is a preventive course. It enhances the obtained therapeutic effect and allows the patient to stay longer in remission. After completing the entire course of chemotherapy, there is a high probability that you will not encounter this disease again.

However, medicine is still not developed enough and the body can behave unpredictably. Thus, there is no possibility of disease recurrence after complete treatment. In this case, another treatment option is offered - bone marrow transplantation.

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